

Rent-sharing, intangibles and digitalization

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Introduction

Despite firms being the crucial place where decisions on the distribution of value are taken, only recently the attention of scholars has been directed to micro-level drivers of wage inequality. One specific segment of the micro-level literature has focused on the role played by the capacity of workers to appropriate rents (e.g., Bell et al, 2023; Card et al., 2018). This paper aims to contribute to this strand of literature focusing on the case of Japan, where the research on rent-sharing has been so far limited (Fukao et al., 2022 and 2023; Dobbelaere and Kiyota, 2018; Tanaka, 2018). We focus our attention on heterogeneity in rent-sharing between firms with high/low-intensity investments in intangible assets and digital technologies.

Methods

The empirical analysis is based on employer-employee matched data obtained by combining Basic Survey on Wage Structure (BSWS) and the Basic Survey of Japanese Business Structure and Activities (BSJBSA). The matching allows for assembling a large longitudinal firm-level dataset over the period 2005-2018 and taking advantage of the many features of panel econometric techniques. Specifically, we employ instrumental variable fixed effects (IV-FE) model in a split sample analysis framework. This allows us, at the same time, to: (i) important identification challenges related to endogeneity/reverse causality of key relationships; (ii) identify the heterogeneity of such relationships in contexts of high/low intensity of intangible ad digitalization.

Results

Our results confirm a positive, generalised and statistically significant rent sharing, with a magnitude aligned to previous studies.

The split sample analysis reveals that companies endowed more with intangible capital and investing more into digital technologies resort more on rent-sharing. This might indicate, in the first place, a complementarity between (at least some types of) labour and more innovative forms of investments; second, a more intensive use of performance-related pay systems by companies that rely on such types of assets, aimed at attracting highly performing workers and at eliciting the expected level of effort; third, that the presence of specific types of investments (particularly, digital technologies) enables the effective implementation of pay-for-performance schemes, that require high efficiency in workers' monitoring, information collection and processing.

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